

INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING SOLFEGGIO

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7376526>

The methodological basis of the discipline "Solfeggio" is made up of traditional forms of work. If some minor innovations are made in the learning process, they are not used by all teachers and are episodic.

How can teaching be revived, the form renewed, and the content of traditional classes emotionally filled ?

The answer is simple and complex at the same time: be creative with your work, using modern interactive teaching methods.

For mental and emotional development, young people are interested in non-standard solutions and vivid impressions that are consonant with their thinking. Modern methodology makes its own adjustments to traditional teaching methods . It is the combination of modern and traditional that makes it possible to attract new forms and methods to existing ones, to actively apply progressive teaching technologies, one of which is interactive methods. Games in which the pedagogical tasks of "Solfeggio" as a musical and theoretical discipline are solved by non-traditional means of education.

Games that you can play in the Solfeggio classes - Guessing, Blitz, Miracles in Music, various types of dominoes, solving crossword puzzles, musical races and much more, depending on the imagination and desire of the teacher. And everyone becomes interested, fun, wants to improve. In the game, memory improves, thinking speeds up, creative activity develops, complexes are removed, mood rises, and as a result, the perception and learning of complex, sometimes abstract concepts, which are so characteristic of the Solfeggio discipline, improves.

In "Guess" the teacher performs auditory analysis in a playful way, where intervals, frets, chords are played for each class, based on the curriculum. Three students participate, on the scoreboard against the guessed task they show the points that the participants in the game receive. If the answer is correct, the teacher plays a major triad, and if the answer is wrong, he plays a glissando, thereby the student exercises self-control. The higher the number of points, the higher the rating, the score. The winner receives a prize - "Lesson Winner" (a ribbon that is worn by the student.) The more difficult the task, the higher the rating. After guessing the task, it should be sung.

The business game "blitz" is held instead of the traditional survey or test. The meaning of this interactive action is reduced to a quick and correct answer that the teacher puts. The students are divided into two teams. Questions are asked to the first team that answers, and the second fixes the correctness of the answers and sets points, then they change roles. This method combines both a survey and a repetition of the material for 10 minutes. In an interactive form, such pedagogical tasks are solved as the ability to clearly and quickly formulate answers, to focus on the opponent's answer, and to put the question correctly. For a short period of the lesson, the teacher gets a complete picture of the preparedness of the group. It is expedient to carry out such games on any musical-theoretical subject.

Miracles in Music follows almost all the rules of the TV game "Field of Miracles", but with musical tasks and symbols on the circle. Moreover, both the leaders and the players are students themselves. Even tasks are compiled by the guys, but with the help of a teacher.

Designations on the circle: lira - prize, whole note - 400 points, half note - 200 points, quarter note - 100, eighth - 50 points, eighth pause - move transition, reprise - points are doubled, bass clef - bankrupt.

The winner is waiting for a prize, which is also determined by all players (most often it is a teacher's encouragement or some kind of stationery).

With great enthusiasm, high school students write a "cognitive" dictation. The genre of the musical fragment, the composition of the ensemble and instruments, the mode, rhythm, range of each part, in what keys it is recorded, and so on, who will hear more and more correctly, is determined. For this, a recording is included: A. Lyadov "Eight Russian Folk Songs" for a symphony orchestra ("Long", "Dance"), E. Grieg - "Peer Gynt", Suite No. 1, ("Dawn", "Anitra's Dance"), F. Mendelssohn - symphony No. 3, part I, main part. Such work contributes to the realization that "Solfeggio" is one of the main subjects in the professional development and formation of young musicians.

And for students of primary and secondary grades, a game is offered - musical dominoes. The teacher makes several types of dominoes, which depict letter designations, letter abbreviations and alterations, tempo designations, which also contributes to the effective assimilation of musical text in the traditional form.

The above interactive modern methods are used in the educational process of the Republican Specialized Music School. V.Uspensky (Tashkent) in the class of the teacher Veziryan E.E. The creative possibilities are endless. Each

teacher has a lot of interesting developments in his creative baggage. The teacher's task is to use them taking into account the individual characteristics of each student, contributing to the creative growth and emotional and psychological emancipation of the personality of a young professional musician, giving joy and pleasure from the Solfeggio classes.

